

PREDICTING NON-LINEAR SHEAR DEFORMATION IN 3D FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

Carolyn Oddy^{1,*}, M. Ekh¹ and M. Fagerström¹

¹Division of Material and Computational Mechanics, Chalmers University of Technology, SE-412 96 Gothenburg, Sweden

*Corresponding author: carolyn.oddy@chalmers.se

Keywords: 3D-woven reinforcement, Finite element modelling, Viscoelasticity

ABSTRACT

The strategic use of 3D-fibre reinforced composite materials has shown promising results. Along with weight efficient stiffness and strength, they have shown encouraging energy absorption capabilities. The following work proposes a general framework for modelling the mechanical response of 3D fibre-reinforced composites. The framework decomposes the stress and strain tensors into two main parts; one driven by the behaviour of the fibre reinforcement, the other driven by the non-linear matrix response under off-axis loading. The non-linear response specifically is introduced into the model using viscoelastic slip planes, in an analogous way to that of a crystal plasticity model. A prototype model is analysed in order to illustrate the capabilities of the proposed framework.

1 INTRODUCTION

To meet increasingly strict emission targets, vehicle manufacturers are turning to lightweight materials to reduce their carbon footprint. Traditional laminated fibre composites, in particular carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP), provide high strength and stiffness relative to weight. These characteristics pave the way for substantial weight reductions. Their use however, presents a number of challenges when it comes to vehicle components that must absorb energy and undergo excessive bending. Laminated composites that are loaded in this manner, are prone to significant delamination due to high inter-laminar stresses. In the event that delamination cracks form and propagate, a significant proportion of the material's energy absorption capability is lost, as this damage mode consumes considerably less energy than e.g. crushing failure.

A class of composite materials with 3D woven reinforcement may help circumvent some of these challenges. As the name suggests, yarns are interlaced in three principal directions. During the weaving process, developed by Khokar [1], warp yarns are interlaced with horizontal weft and vertical weft yarns in a grid-like set. Along with providing weight efficient stiffness and strength characteristics, 3D fibre-reinforced composites have shown promising energy absorption capabilities. For example Khokar et al. [2] have shown that, in bending, a 3D-CFRP I-beam has two to three times the specific energy absorption capability of a steel I-beam with equivalent geometry. The fibre networks suppress delamination and allow for stable and progressive damage growth in a quasi-ductile manner.

As the concept design for future vehicles is largely simulation driven, developing an efficient computational model of the material behaviour is key to supporting the widespread adoption of 3D fibre-reinforced composites in industry. The model must be capable of describing how the 3D reinforced material deforms and is damaged under mechanical stress. In particular it must predict the inelastic process that leads to energy absorption. With the ultimate goal of developing a macroscale homogenised model to predict how the material deforms and eventually fails under loading, this work presents a general framework for macroscopic modelling of the mechanical response of this class of materials. In this framework, material non-linearity can be conveniently incorporated. Specifically, a candidate for a phenomenologically based orthotropic viscoelastic model is proposed. Specific emphasis is thereby given to predicting the non-linear deformation behaviour of the 3D fibre-reinforced composite under shear loading, using crystal plasticity inspired slip planes.

2 MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS

A sketch of a typical construct of this class of 3D-woven reinforcement is presented in Fig. 1. It consists of three sets of yarns: warp yarns (blue) extending in the weaving direction as well as horizontal weft (red) and vertical weft (green) yarns extending transversely to the weave in the width and thickness directions respectively.

Figure 1: Sketches of the 3D-woven reinforcement, created in TexGen [3]. Blue yarns are warp, green and red yarns are horizontal and vertical weft.

This weaving technique allows for the direct manufacturing of complex fibre preforms with various cross section geometries that can be tailored to the overall needs of the desired component [4]. The inherent nature of the weaving technique therefore lends itself well to the strategic combination of both two and three dimensional weaves as well as local variations in yarn orientation in a single component. While 2D weaves are not explicitly discussed in this paper, developing a method which allows for a convenient and consistent way to formulate a model for both 2D and 3D weaves while capturing varying yarn orientations, would provide a promising base for further model developments and additions.

Preliminary experimental results [5] also indicate that this class of 3D fibre-reinforced composites exhibits linear material behaviour when loaded along one of the three nominal reinforcement directions. Off-axis or shear loading however, produces a prominent non-linear response. This is likely due to the viscoelastic behaviour and eventual damage of the matrix material. Accounting for this non-linear viscoelastic shear behaviour is an essential first step to developing an accurate computational model of the overall behaviour of this class of material.

3 MODEL FORMULATION

3.1 Preliminaries

In both [6] and [7] Spencer focuses on continuum theories that describe the macroscopic behaviour of fibre-reinforced materials. In particular he proposes a method to decompose the stress tensor in a way that allows for the separation of linear material behaviour in the reinforcement directions from possible nonlinear behaviour under off-axis or shear loading. This decomposition has later been utilised by Nedjar [8], Vogler et al. [9] and Camanho et al. [10]. They, respectively, used the proposed decomposition to develop a viscoelasticity model, a plasticity model as well as three-dimensional failure criteria for unidirectional composites.

3.1.1 Decomposition of stress tensor for unidirectional composites

Starting from a unidirectional fibre-reinforced material with a single family of reinforcement fibres oriented along a vector \mathbf{a} , Spencer proposed the following decomposition of the stress tensor:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{s} + p\mathbf{1} + T\mathbf{M}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ denotes the second order identity tensor and \mathbf{M} the second order structural tensor defined as:

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{a}. \quad (2)$$

By introducing the part \mathbf{s} as being deviatoric and without any resulting contribution in the fibre direction, i.e. fulfilling

$$\mathbf{s} : \mathbf{1} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{s} : \mathbf{M} = 0, \quad (4)$$

this part naturally incorporates any nonlinear response (resulting from the matrix) due to off-axis (shear) loading of the unidirectional composite. Furthermore, the last term in Equation (1), i.e. $T\mathbf{M}$, contributes to the stress in the direction of the fibres and $p\mathbf{1}$ is the remaining part of the stress of volumetric type. To be explicit, by combining Eqs. (1), (3) and (4), it can be shown that:

$$p = \frac{1}{2} (\text{tr}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}] - [\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{M}]) \quad (5)$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} (3[\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{M}] - \text{tr}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]), \quad (6)$$

where $\text{tr}[\bullet] = \bullet : \mathbf{1}$ is the trace of \bullet .

Although the use of structural tensors means that the proposed theory hold no restriction to specific geometry or local fibre arrangements we clarify that for a material with fibre direction along the first main axis, i.e. $\mathbf{a} = [1 \ 0 \ 0]^T$, then the stress decomposition becomes (on matrix form):

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \sigma_{12} & \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{12} & \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33}) & \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} & \sigma_{23} & \frac{1}{2}(-\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{s}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})}_{p} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{(\sigma_{11} - \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}))}_{T} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

3.1.2 Decomposition of strain tensor for unidirectional composites

Nedjar [8] later showed that for transversely isotropic composite materials (again with fibres aligned along \mathbf{a}), it is also convenient to decompose the strain tensor in a similar way:

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathbf{e} + \zeta\mathbf{1} + \xi\mathbf{M}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{e} fulfills:

$$\mathbf{e} : \mathbf{1} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{e} : \mathbf{M} = 0, \quad (9)$$

from which also explicit expressions for ζ and ξ can be derived (similar as for p and T above).

By imposing this strain decomposition and linear elastic transverse isotropy it follows that \mathbf{s} only depends on \mathbf{e} and not on the total strain $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$, i.e.

$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{s}(\mathbf{e}). \quad (10)$$

As a consequence, by decomposing the stress and strain tensor this way, it becomes possible to identify and incorporate material behaviours in the appropriate components in a physically meaningful way. This can include e.g. viscoelasticity, plasticity, damage initiation and propagation driven by various material failure modes. Noteworthy for the ongoing model development aimed at composites with 3D reinforcements is that these decompositions extended to 3D allow for a convenient inclusion of shear driven matrix viscoelasticity in the pertinent stress and strain components.

3.2 Extension to 3D fibre-reinforced viscoelastic composites

3.2.1 Elastic orthotropy

As previously mentioned, the nature of the considered 3D fibre-reinforcement produces a material with three preferred directions, each having their own unique properties. Modeling this class of material therefore requires the use of a fully orthotropic stiffness tensor. Furthermore, defining the orthotropic stiffness through the use of structural tensors provides a flexible formulation which allows for local variations in reinforcement orientation at each material and/or integration point.

Let us now consider an orthotropic material with three preferred directions (in this case the three reinforcement directions), defined by the mutually orthogonal vectors \mathbf{a}_1 , \mathbf{a}_2 and \mathbf{a}_3 . By introducing three associated second order structural tensors

$$\mathbf{M}_1 = \mathbf{a}_1 \otimes \mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{M}_2 = \mathbf{a}_2 \otimes \mathbf{a}_2 \text{ and } \mathbf{M}_3 = \mathbf{a}_3 \otimes \mathbf{a}_3 \quad (11)$$

the fourth order orthotropic stiffness tensor can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{E} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \varphi_i \mathbf{A}^i + \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 \phi_{ij} \mathbf{M}_i \otimes \mathbf{M}_j, \quad (12)$$

where the fourth order tensor \mathbf{A}^i is given by

$$\mathbf{A}^i = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{M}_i \bar{\otimes} \mathbf{1} + \mathbf{1} \bar{\otimes} \mathbf{M}_i). \quad (13)$$

Although the aforementioned representation of the orthotropic elastic stiffness does not directly involve the common elastic engineering parameters (Young's moduli, shear moduli and Poisson's ratios), it is emphasised that the coefficients φ_i and ϕ_{ij} , can easily be related to the engineering parameters simply by considering the case where the three reinforcement directions correspond to the main coordinate axes, i.e. where $\mathbf{a}_1 = \mathbf{e}_1$, $\mathbf{a}_2 = \mathbf{e}_2$ and $\mathbf{a}_3 = \mathbf{e}_3$.

Finally, the constitutive stress - strain relationship for elastic orthotropy using the considered structural tensors can be expressed as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \varphi_i \mathbf{A}^i : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 \phi_{ij} (\mathbf{M}_j : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}) \mathbf{M}_i. \quad (14)$$

3.2.2 Decomposition of stress and strain tensors

In his work, Spencer showed that by following the same thought process and procedures, his methodology can be used beyond unidirectional composites to describe the macroscopic behaviour of increasingly complex fibre-reinforced materials. In the case of the considered 3D fibre-reinforced composite, the stress decomposition would then become:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{s} + p\mathbf{1} + \sum_{i=1}^3 T_i \mathbf{M}_i, \quad (15)$$

where p and T_i may be determined through

$$s : \mathbf{1} = 0 \text{ and } s : \mathbf{M}_i = 0, \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (16)$$

Note however, that it can conveniently be shown that for the current case of mutually orthogonal fibre reinforcements, the decomposition of the stress tensor can (without further loss of generality) be simplified to:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{s} + \sum_{i=1}^3 T_i \mathbf{M}_i, \quad (17)$$

where

$$T_i = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{M}_i. \quad (18)$$

For clarity, consider the decomposition given in Equations (17) and (18) for a material point in which the local yarn orientations are given by the principal coordinate axes. Specifically, that is where $\mathbf{a}_1 = \mathbf{e}_1$, $\mathbf{a}_2 = \mathbf{e}_2$ and $\mathbf{a}_3 = \mathbf{e}_3$. This gives (on matrix form) that

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \sigma_{12} & \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{12} & 0 & \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} & \sigma_{23} & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_s + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{T_1 \mathbf{M}_1} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{T_2 \mathbf{M}_2} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{33} \end{bmatrix}}_{T_3 \mathbf{M}_3}. \quad (19)$$

As can be seen, the stress is then again decomposed into one term driven by the shear stresses in the material and three terms driven by the stresses along the three reinforcement directions.

What remains now is to fully define the constitutive relationship of the material according to this decomposition. To do so, we extend the strain decomposition by Nedjar to three dimensions as:

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathbf{e} + \sum_{i=1}^3 (\boldsymbol{\epsilon} : \mathbf{M}_i) \mathbf{M}_i, \quad (20)$$

where now

$$\mathbf{e} : \mathbf{1} = 0 \text{ and } \mathbf{e} : \mathbf{M}_i = 0, \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (21)$$

Similarly as for the stress, the first term in the decomposition, Equation (20), holds the shear strain components while the final three terms hold the strain components in the reinforcement directions.

By imposing the stress and strain decomposition in Equations (17) and (20) on the stress-strain relation in Equation (14), it can be shown that

$$\mathbf{s} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \varphi_i \mathbf{A}^i : \mathbf{e} \quad (22)$$

and that the stresses along the reinforcement directions (T_i) are given by

$$T_i = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{M}_i = \varphi_i (\boldsymbol{\epsilon} : \mathbf{M}_i) + \sum_{j=1}^3 \phi_{ij} (\boldsymbol{\epsilon} : \mathbf{M}_j). \quad (23)$$

Note that it again has been advantageously shown that \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{e} can be directly related to one another without any additional coupling to other strain components.

From Equations (22) and (23) it can also be shown that it is possible to formulate a decomposed constitutive equation of the following form

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{E}_m : \boldsymbol{e} + \mathbf{E}_f : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \quad (24)$$

where

$$\mathbf{E}_m = \sum_{i=1}^3 \varphi_i \mathbf{A}^i, \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_f = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\varphi_i \mathbf{M}_i \otimes \mathbf{M}_i + \sum_{j=1}^3 \phi_{ij} \mathbf{M}_i \otimes \mathbf{M}_j \right). \quad (26)$$

3.2.3 Extension to nonlinear viscoelastic behaviour

The nonlinear behaviour of a 3D reinforced composite is driven by matrix shearing while the fibre bundles remain largely linear elastic. It is then natural to assume a viscoelastic behaviour only through the relation between s and e . Inspired by Nedjar [8], we propose to consider e as additively decomposed into an elastic and a viscoelastic part

$$\boldsymbol{e} = \boldsymbol{e}^e + \boldsymbol{e}^{ve} \quad (27)$$

whereby the stress-strain relation in Equation (24) transforms into:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{E}_m : (\boldsymbol{e} - \boldsymbol{e}^{ve}) + \mathbf{E}_f : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \quad (28)$$

The evolution of the viscoelastic strain should govern the matrix driven nonlinear shear behaviour of the model. However, the resulting linear behaviour observed when the material is loaded along the reinforcement directions must also be preserved. A model inspired by crystal plasticity with viscoelastic slip planes is then proposed. As such, it is assumed that viscoelastic strain should strictly develop when there is pronounced shear loading in preferred material planes (local 12-, 13- and 23-planes defined by the nominal directions of the warp (\boldsymbol{a}_1), horizontal weft (\boldsymbol{a}_2) and vertical weft (\boldsymbol{a}_3) yarns c.f. Fig. 1). These shear slip planes, denoted by I, are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Illustration of the considered slip planes and shear traction vector

To restrict the development of viscoelastic strain to the preferred planes, the following Norton type model, is considered:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{e}}^{ve} = \sum_{I=1}^3 \underbrace{\frac{1}{t_*^I} \left(\frac{|t_s^I|}{\kappa^I} \right)^{n^I}}_{\text{magnitude}} \underbrace{\boldsymbol{m}^I}_{\text{direction}} \quad (29)$$

The magnitude of the viscoelastic slip rate is thereby assumed to be driven by the magnitude of the shear traction, $|t_s^I|$, in each slip plane. We also assume that the direction of the slip rate, m^I follows the direction of maximum dissipation, i.e.

$$m^I = \frac{\partial |t_s^I|}{\partial s}. \quad (30)$$

In this model, the relaxation time t_*^I , the exponent n^I and the drag stress (or slip resistance) κ^I are all parameters that control the non-linear viscous behaviour of the model. Although in the simplest case it is assumed to be constant for each slip plane, we note that κ^I may depend on the slip rate direction and may also be considered to evolve during the deformation.

4 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

To demonstrate the main characteristics of the proposed model, consider a case of uniaxial tension with the warp direction varying from 0° (parallel to the loading direction) to 90° (perpendicular to the loading direction). This is indicated in Fig. 3.

For this example, elastic properties similar to a 3D fibre-reinforced carbon-epoxy earlier reported by Ekermann et al. [5] are chosen. As for the viscoelastic parameters, we adopt a fixed set of parameters in common for all slip systems that clearly demonstrate the model behaviour¹. Future experiments will be performed to identify more accurate parameter values for the material systems of interest. All the parameters related to the example are summarised in Table 1 wherein the warp, horizontal weft and vertical weft are denoted by 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Stiffness	E_1	90 [GPa]	E_2	20 [GPa]	E_3	20 [GPa]
Shear stiffness	G_{12}	3.2 [GPa]	G_{13}	3.4 [GPa]	G_{23}	2.3 [GPa]
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.16 [-]	ν_{13}	0.25 [-]	ν_{23}	0.33 [-]
Viscous parameters	t_*	$10^{6.5}$ [s]	κ	2 [MPa]	n	2 [-]

Table 1: Material parameters used for the numerical example.

As can be seen from the model response shown in Fig. 3, the model yields a linear elastic response when the load is applied at 0° and 90° degrees. When loaded at 45° degrees the model instead shows a softer, more pronounced non-linear response.

¹Please note that although the viscoelastic model generally allows for three parameters per slip system, we simplify here to the situation where all systems to have the same viscoelastic characteristics. Furthermore, as strain-rate effects are not studied, we simply choose $t_* = 10^{6.5}$ s.

Figure 3: Stress strain curves under uniaxial stress for varying fibre orientations.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The current contribution proposes a framework for modelling the mechanical response of 3D fibre-reinforced composites. The framework is based on a decomposition of the stress and strain tensor, assuming three nominal reinforcement directions, analogous to the the propositions for unidirectional composites (with one reinforcement direction) by Spencer [6, 7] and Nedjar [8]. By adopting the stress and strain tensor decompositions, the modelling framework conveniently allows for the separation of the model response into two parts. Specially, one which drives an initially linear response when loaded in the fibre reinforcement directions and a second which drives a nonlinear material response under any off-axis loading.

To demonstrate the capabilities of the modelling framework a prototype model is analysed, which provides a linearly elastic response when loaded along any of the reinforcement directions, whereas viscoelastic shearing occurs under off-axis loading. The nonlinear viscoelastic response is introduced to the model as viscoelastic slip along predefined shear (or slip) planes in the material similar to a model for crystal-plasticity.

The framework presented is general. It allows for additional non-linearity to be added, e.g. if the apparent macroscopic material response shows plastic behaviour. It also allows for a rather straightforward implementation of damage mechanisms and provides a natural way to separate between failure mechanisms associated with the reinforcements and those associated with the matrix material.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Khokar, 3D-Weaving: Theory and Practice, *Journal of the Textile Institute* **92**, 2001 , pp. 193-207.
- [2] N. Khokar, F. Winberg and S. Hallström, Novel 3D preform architecture for performance and reliability of structural beams, *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Composite Materials ICCM20, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19-24, 2015*.
- [3] L. Brown and M. Sherburn, Texgen v3.9.0, Zenodo 2017. doi:<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.291485>.
- [4] S. Kazemahvazi, N. Khokar, S. Hallström, H.N.G. Wadley, and V.S. Deshpande, Confluent 3D-assembly of fibrous structures. *Composites Science and Technology*, **127**, 2016, pp. 95-105.

- [5] T. Ekermann and S. Hallström, Mechanical characterisation of composites with 3D-woven reinforcement, *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Composite Materials ICCM20, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19-24, 2015*.
- [6] A. Spencer, *Deformation of Fibre-Reinforced Materials*, Clarendon Press, 1972.
- [7] A. Spencer. *Constitutive Theory for Strongly Anisotropic Solids, In: Continuum Theory of the Mechanics of Fibre-Reinforced Composites.*, CISM Courses and Lecture No.282, 1984.
- [8] B. Nedjar, A time dependent model of unidirectional fibre-reinforced composites with viscoelastic matrices, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **48**, 2011, pp. 2333-2339.
- [9] M. Vogler, R. Rolfes, P. Camanho, Modeling the inelastic deformation and fracture of polymer composites - Part 1: plasticity model, *Mechanics of Materials*, **59**, 2013, pp. 50-64.
- [10] P. Camanho, A. Arterio, A. Melro, G. Catalanotti and M. Vogler, Three-dimensional invariant-based failure criteria for fibre-reinforced composites, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **55**, 2015, pp. 92-107.